

Emerging Country CEOs' Cognitively Deep State and Environmentalism: Experiment Setting in Precariat Behaviours to Finance ESG Investments

Short Runnings: CEOs' Cognitively Deep State and Environmentalism

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Data Availability Statement

The datasets generated during and/or analysed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Declarations of Conflicting Interests

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest, including financial interests.

Ethics Approval Statement

This study ensured that all research processes complied with ethical clearance requirements, as confirmed by the issuance of a clearance certificate by the relevant committee. This study involved human participants in a low-risk behavioural experiment. All participants provided informed consent and met the specific inclusion criteria for accounting experience. The study ensured anonymity, confidentiality, and voluntary participation throughout and was conducted in accordance with institutional ethical guidelines.

Authors' Contributions

SS: conceptual design, analysis and interpretation, completeness and accuracy, and finalising.

ENSH: data collection, drafting work, analysis and interpretation, and statistical analysis.